

Purification of SLC40A1 from Expi293F™ Cells

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Protocol description

This protocol is used to purify the SLC transporter expressed in Expi293F™ Cells using detergent solubilization followed by a series of different chromatographic methods. Depending on the nature of the expression construct and experimental requirements, the GFP tag can be removed using a proteolytic reaction.

Materials

Biological materials:	
Reagents:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ HEPES (Apollo Scientific, catalog number BI8181)▪ NaCl (Sigma Aldrich, catalog number S9888)▪ Cholesteryl Hemisuccinate Tris Salt (CHS) (Anatrace, catalog number CH210)▪ OGNG (Octyl Glucose Neopentyl Glycol) (Anatrace, catalog number NG311)▪ cOmplete™, EDTA-free Protease Inhibitor Cocktail (Roche, catalog number 11873580001)▪ Glycerol (Sigma Aldrich, catalog number G5516)▪ TALON® Metal Affinity Resin, (Takara Bio, catalog number 635653)▪ TEV (Tobacco Etch Virus) protease (produced in-house)▪ PD 10 Desalting Columns (Sigma Aldrich, catalog number GE17-0851-01)
Equipment:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Gravity flow columns▪ 50 kDa cut-off centrifugal concentrators▪ 96 well block (2 mL)▪ WHEATON® Dounce Tissue Grinder, 40 mL (DWK Life Sciences, catalog number 357546)▪ AVESTIN - EMULSIFLEX-C3 (C3 homogeniser) (Wolflabs, catalog number EF-C3)

Reagents setup

- **Stock solution:** 10% (w/v) OGNG/CHS in the ratio of 10:1, prepared in Base buffer. Rotate at 4 °C overnight to allow complete solubilisation and store at -20 °C.
- Base buffer (50 mM MES pH 6.0, 250 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol)
- Strep wash buffer (50 mM MES pH 6.0, 250 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 0.145% OGNG/CHS)
- Strep elution buffer (50 mM MES pH 6.0, 250 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 0.145% OGNG/CHS, 100 mM Biotin)
- SEC buffer (20 mM MES-NaOH pH 6.0, 200 mM NaCl, 0.087% OGNG/CHS), filtered through 0.22 µm membrane

Procedure

▪ Part A of protocol / day 1

1. Thaw the frozen cell pellet in a water bath set to room temperature.
2. Add lysis buffer by adding 3 tablets of Protease Inhibitor Cocktail tablet to 150 mL of base buffer. Allow the tablets to dissolve.
3. Suspend thawed pellets with lysis buffer and pour into a Dounce homogeniser. Homogenise the solution by pulling and pushing the plunger up and down approximately 20 times. Keep on ice.

4. Break the cells by passing through a **C3** homogenizer at **10,000 psi** pressure 2 times. Keep on ice.
5. Add OGNG/CHS stock solution to the lysed cells to a final concentration of 1% OGNG/0.1% CHS.
4. Rotate the container slowly for 1 hour at 4 °C.
5. Centrifuge the solution at 50,000 x g for 30 min at 4 °C.
6. Equilibrate 4-6 mL bed volume of Strep resin with the base buffer.
7. Collect the supernatant and add equilibrated Strep resin to the supernatant, rotate for 1 hour at 4 °C.
8. Transfer the solution to a gravity flow column, allow the solution to flow through.
9. Wash the resin with 10 times the bed volume of Strep wash buffer.
10. Perform 3-4 serial elutions with 3-5 mL of strep elution buffer each. Let the column stand for 15-20 minutes between each elution.
11. Measure protein concentration using nanodrop. If the protein has a TEV cleavage site followed by a GFP tag (and if the GFP tag needs removal), add TEV protease to the protein solution in a 1:5 to 1:10 (w/w) TEV:protein ratio.
12. Slowly rotate the container overnight at 4 °C.

▪ **Part B of protocol / day 2**

13. In a gravity flow column, equilibrate 2-4 mL bed volume of TALON resin with SEC buffer.
14. Add equilibrated TALON resin to the overnight TEV reaction mixture and rotate for 1 hour at 4 °C.
15. Using an empty gravity flow column let the solution collect flow through solution in a 100 kDa cut-off centrifugal filter.
16. Concentrate the solution by centrifuging at 3,000 xg at 4 °C, stop and gently agitate every 5 minutes.
17. Equilibrate a Superose 6 Increase 10/300 GL column using SEC buffer.
18. Concentrate the sample down to the desired injection volume and inject the sample into the sample loop.
19. Run a SEC elution.
20. Pool peak fractions in a fresh 100 kDa cut-off centrifugal concentrator and concentrate to the required volume/concentration at 3,000 xg at 4 °C.

Additional notes

1. The amount of solubilisation buffer depends on the cell pellet volume. We recommend using 30-40 mL solubilisation buffer per litre cell culture. The above protocol has been adapted for cell pellet from 4 L culture.
2. The TEV treatment step is to be carried out only if the GFP tag needs to be removed.

Data availability

References

Please write to contact@re-solute.eu in case of questions or errors.